

Design and development broadband monopole antenna for in-door application

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the broadband monopole antenna refers to a signal wideband of the frequencies, which can be divided the signal into channels of the frequency bins. Aim this paper to design and development broadband monopole antenna. The monopole antenna was designed by adding slot to the radiated patch antenna with a single feed line, which reduced the size and the design complexity. A rectangular patch antenna was presented using feed line to decrease the ground plane with a suitable gap distance. The broadband monopole antenna was designed with a frequency range of 800 MHz – 3 GHz, with Bandwidth 0.66 (dB), reflection coefficients and return loss. The frequency-dependent characteristic impedance was included. It can be used in various broadband applications in used commercially for various communication systems such as 4G (LTE), WiMAX and WLAN (LTE), remote sensing, biomedical, and mobile wireless. Apart from that, this technology is environment-friendly; an antenna which consists of reception and transmission. The antenna is simulated by using computer simulation (CST) software; using FR-4 substrate of 4.4 permittivity thickness 1.6 mm and loss tangent of 0.025. The measurement result is accepted with simulation result, proving the acceptable broadband operation for this proposed structure.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Today, mobile phone users are reaping the benefits from the tremendous growth in the demand for high-speed and broad-band data services such as high-speed browsing, high definition videos, and video calls [1–4]. According to statistics more than 80% of mobile data traffic comes from domestic environment, such as the commercial buildings and airports. Therefore, internally distributed antenna systems, (IDAS) have

become even more sought after to provide, wireless communication coverage in high-traffic areas [5–8]. IDAS is a broadband network connected to a common source via a coaxial cable to improve coverage. Several vertically polarized antenna designs are proposed for IDAS and discussed in the open literature [9–11].

The evolution of a multi-polar MIMO antenna system with two multi-purpose components for AP wireless applications in the range of 2.3–9 GHz was studied. The proposed system included single pole antennas with a wide-angle microstrip antenna having a common radiate element and a ground plane due to alternative coupling. New parasitic elements were introduced to increase isolation between the ports. Expected bandwidth coverage for Wi-Fi and LTE applications [12–14].

With rapid development of modern mobile wireless industry, the request for broadband services and high-speed data services are increasing [15]. For most mobile data, as traffic are generated in internal environment, distributed antennas play an increasingly important role in internal wireless communication systems. In addition, in order to provide better telecommunication services, more frequency bands have been designed and used commercially for various communication systems such as 4G WiMAX and WLAN. Therefore, there is a need for broadband distribution antennas that can cover multiple service ranges simultaneously [5, 16, 17]. This paper discusses the a broadband antenna with double casing load for indoor mobile, communications system [10]. The purpose is to cover wider frequency bands (698–960 and 1710–2300 MHz in [18], 800–1100 and 1700–2580 MHz in [19]), but the bandwidth are still not wide enough to be used in LTE applications in the unlicensed spectrum of LTE-U and LTE, LAA applications [20, 21].

Diversity in current LTE systems is typically limited to two antennas per radio, enough to ensure that, if an antenna is in an RF vacuum, the other antenna is not normally available, providing better performance in a multi-track environment. Antenna diversity with LTE is used to defend against multiple pathways, reduce interruptions, and improve the quality and the reliability of communication links [13, 22–25]. Dual broadband antenna for internal LTE terminals. The antenna consists of three separate radiated elements a rectangular upper plate with two U-shaped slots, two long rectangular openings to cover the upper range of 1700–2700 MHz, and two low-reflective L-Shaped components used to cover the low frequency range of 800–960 MHz. The proposed antenna is expected to be applied directly to all portable and wireless systems, including 2G, 3G, 4G LTE, and Wi-Fi [26]. With the development of hand-held devices, rapid development has emerged, and device appearances must be attractive and compact. The antenna can be described as a device that converts the electromagnetic wave in the antenna into radiation in an unlimited medium [27]. Due to the exponential growth of wireless systems, mobile phone antennas should be smaller and widely supported for LTE systems for wide area network (WWAN) as its performance is at least 100 MB/s in 100 high data rate links with 50 Mbps in transmission [28].

In recent years, internal antenna technology has been growing due to the evolution of wireless communications such as WiFi, WiMAX, 3G, 4G, LTE, and WLAN. In addition to the rapid growth in the number of wireless terminals in buildings, airports, and conference rooms, researchers also need antennas to meet the requirements for internal antennas such as high performance (gain, efficiency), effective data rates, broadband, and one-way [29]. The proposed broadband bandwidth are sufficient for all mobile system services, namely, GSM/UMTS LTE, including LTE bands 42–43 (3400–3800 MHz) and LTE-U/LTE-LAA (5150–5850 MHz). The proposed antenna is characterised by four conditions of annular antenna [30, 31]. Monopole antennas ideally give omnidirectional patterns [32]. The condition of not stimulating anything other than placing the first higher order complicates the feeding process of the traditional, microstrip LWA [33]. Characterization of simulation using CST Microwave Studio; analysis and comparison of results [34, 35].

In this paper, the broadband monopole antenna was designed with the operating frequency band from 800 MHz to 3 GHz. These frequencies are chosen for the applications of 4G LTE indoor buildings. The main objective, of this paper is to provide the highest possible antenna gain. Finally, the proposed antenna was fabricated and tested and do comparisons between the results. For future work to provide as high as possible of the antenna gain, the gain and bandwidth (BW) can be increased through many techniques. The most common technique is the doing monopole, stack, adding a slot.

2. ANTENNA CONFIGURATION

Figure 1 (a) shows the geometric dimensions of broadband monopole antenna at the frequency range of 800 MHz – 3 GHz for LTE applications. The back view for monopole antenna is shown in Figure 1 (b). Figure 2 shows the integrated fabricated antenna, fed and printed on an FR4. The substrate and copper of dielectric constant, $\epsilon_r = 4.4$ with thickness, $h_s = 1.6$ mm, where the length and the width of the substrate = 99.53 mm, and the length of the substrate = 84.35 mm. The length and the width for copper, $w_s = 99.53$ mm, $l_s = 84.73$ mm, $h_t = 0.035$, loss tangent of 0.02, with transmission line driven by 50 Ω .

antenna achieved better reflection coefficients (-20 dB and -10 dB) at 800 MHz and 3 GHz compared to the measurement method where the monopole antenna only achieved reflection coefficients (-15.651 dB and -20 dB) at 804 MHz and 3 GHz. The comparison results are shown in Table 2. The broadband monopole antenna has two gains in frequency 2 GHz as shown in Figure 3, and frequency 2.8 GHz shown in Figure 4. Simulation process whereas the gain in measurement process is dB. Both processes provided different gains due to power loss in the FR4 board as mentioned previously. This table explains simulation results for reflection coefficients, bandwidth, and return loss. Figure 5 as compared between simulation and measured result for the broadband monopole antenna.

Table 2. Comparison simulation and measurement broadband monopole antenna

Antenna parameters	Simulation broadband monopole-antenna		Measurement broadband monopole antenna	
Resonant frequency	800 MHz	3 GHz	804 MHz	3 GHz
Reflection coefficient RL (dB)	-20 dB	-10 dB	-15.651 dB	-20 dB
Bandwidth, BW (%)	0.66		0.75	

Figure 3. Radiation pattern for 1st band 2 GHz for monopole antenna

Figure 4. Radiation pattern for 2.8 GHz for monopole antenna

Figure 5. Comparison of simulation results with measurement for monopole antenna

4. CONCLUSION

This paper discusses the design and the development of short-range communication devices using the broadband monopole antenna. Short-range communication systems that served to transmit and receive at these frequency bands were chosen from 800 MHz to 3 GHz. Hence, these frequencies are chosen for 4G LTE applications for in-door buildings. Furthermore, the response of the design was optimized in order to get appropriate outputs of S-parameter and gain. The result of the antenna seemed to be inconsistent with the original hypothesis since the frequency resulting through the lap measurement test is somehow begin shifted to a different frequency with a different return loss. With that, the gain received also is different through calculation compared to the simulation. The difference in the results between the simulation and measurement is due to some factors that many have been contributed starting from the fabrication process such as the soldering process, measurement process, and the FR4 tolerance.

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